

Sustainable Carbon Accounting & Taxation Aspects in India

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Abstract

Global warming now is the biggest threat facing the planet earth. With rapid industrialization and growth of the global economy, the CO₂ level in the atmosphere has risen to alarming levels. To neutralize the release of harmful gases into the atmosphere, leaders of all nations have taken a significant pledge and initiative called carbon credit. Kyoto protocol came into being with the objective to reduce the damages caused by climatic change. With the idea of carbon credit, several allied issues surfaced with respect to how the accounting issues of these credits need to be accounted for. At present, there are no accounting standards or interpretations that specifically deal with the carbon credits. The organization, therefore, has to apply judgments and adopt the best practices or standards laid down by their country specific accounting bodies. Very recently a number of accounting practices have emerged but different approaches make the comparison and interpretation of accounting results a difficult task. A distinct framework for carbon credit accounting is needed to make the transactions in carbon credits transparent and making the financial statements understandable by all the stakeholders. The major objective of carbon accounting is to establish a formal structure within organizations for climate change strategy, identify carbon-related risks and opportunities, introduce carbon management systems and finally achieve carbon reduction targets.

Keywords: Carbon credit, Greenhouse gases, Emission, Carbon trading, Kyoto protocol, Carbon Management.

Introduction

All countries across the globe have realized the need to combat global warming, erratic climatic change and the harmful effects of greenhouse gases. Sustainable development is difficult to achieve without balancing environmental damage and degradation. Political and national leadership across the globe have of late recognized the need to contain the spread and concentration of greenhouse gases. International consensus is in place to tackle the crisis of environmental degradation and all countries have adopted and ratified the Kyoto Protocol. Greenhouse Emission gases would come at a cost. All polluters who are below the prescribed threshold will be able to trade in and hold some commodity of potential value. Simply put, carbon can now be traded and tracked like any other commodity. In 1997 the Kyoto Protocol was adopted and imposed binding obligations on Industrialized Countries. It envisaged the need to reduce the emission of six greenhouse gases, carbon dioxide (CO₂) methane (CH₄) nitrous

oxide (N₂O) hydrofluorocarbon (HFCs) perfluorocarbon (PFCs) and Sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆). In order to encourage participation from all countries both in the public and the private sector, the protocol suggested three market-based mechanisms – The emissions trading, clean development mechanism, and joint implementation efforts. Article 17 of the Kyoto Protocol under (IET) International Emission Trading, lays down that Countries can acquire emission units from others and use them towards meeting their targets. An International transaction log is developed which will ensure the transfer of emission reduction units between countries. Environmental analysts are of the opinion that this will lead to the creation of a systematic emissions market worldwide. Article 6 of Joint Implementation (JI) lays down that Countries can undertake emission reduction or emission removal projects in any other country that is obliged under the protocol and count the emission units in order to meet its own target under the protocol. Joint implementation is the collaborative effort of the participating countries ratified under the protocol. One ton of Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) is equal to one Emission reduction units (ERU). However, all ERUs should be tangible and capable of measurement, verification, or third party audit. Article 12 of the mechanism under clean development, lays down the rules for advanced and highly industrialized countries to implementation of emission reduction projects in developing countries and earn credits in the form of certified emission reduction (CERs). The CERs earned can be utilized towards their own emission reduction target. CDM has the twin benefit of helping the developing countries in sustainable development as well and contributes to the goal of reducing the concentration of greenhouse gases.

Carbon Credit, Carbon Offset & Carbon Trading

A carbon credit is the equivalent unit of one ton of carbon dioxide (CO₂) or release of other harmful greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. Business houses who have exceeded the quotas of emission are allowed to purchase carbon credits (CC) from the open market and if there are any surplus credits remaining with them it can be sold in the open market. This process of exchange of carbon credits is called carbon trading. Business Houses can freely trade carbon credits similar to financial instruments and improves their scope of earning additional revenue by selling carbon credits. Organizations can voluntarily participate in the carbon trading market in order to reduce their carbon footprint. Trading in carbon credits can also be seen as a system to penalize Organizations and Countries who are causing excessive pollution and at the same time rewarding those who are actively taking steps to control pollution. Carbon offset, on the other hand, is the real tangible method to compensate for the amount of carbon dioxide pollution that the business is causing by preventing the pollution somewhere else on the earth. Carbon offsets could be by way of setting up a wind power project, an urban or a rural electrification project, biomass project, an afforestation drive or an initiative to preserve the forests or the ecology. Recent experiences show that Countries buying carbon credits are the World's worst polluters and Countries selling carbon credits are the ones who have adopted the cleaner, more greener and sustainable technologies, and processes. This mechanism has enabled Organizations and Countries at large to contain the levels of emissions worldwide and the threats of global warming can be effectively handled using this system. Kyoto protocol mandates three types of carbon credits. First the Certified Emission Reduction (CER) a unit of carbon credit authorized by UNFCCC. CERs can be held in electronic forms and traded in the open market. Second, the Assigned Amounts Unit (AAU) where the member countries are assigned the emission target of CO₂. One unit of AAU is equivalent to one metric ton of CO₂ but cannot be traded. The third is the Emission Reduction Unit (ERU) the unit of reduction of CO₂ or greenhouse gases. ERU units are tradeable units among the member nations executed by entering into transfer agreements for environment-friendly technologies or through joint implementation efforts of the participating countries.

The trading platform for CERs is the Multi Commodity Exchange (MCX) and the National commodity & derivatives exchange (NCDEX). These exchanges will also enable Indian firms to get a better price for their carbon credits and integrate with the global markets to ensure best practices in emissions trading. There are various parties involved in the carbon trading process. First, the generating entity or generator that is the entity that undertakes CDM activity to generate CERs. Second, The CDM executive board of UNFCCC which approves the CDM projects and issues CERs. Third, designated national Authority (DNA) and in India, it is the National CDM authority under the Ministry of Environment, Forests and climate change (MOEF). Fourth, designated operational entities (DOE) which validate and verify the CDM projects and its operations. Fifth, the buying entity or the buyer which purchases the CERs generated by the generating entity. India is the world's third leading emitter of greenhouse gases. India has ratified the Paris agreement and pledged to reduce emission intensity by 33-35% within the year 2030. Also, it plans 40% of the installed electricity capacity to be renewable or nuclear by 2030. [1]

Carbon Management Accounting (CMA)

Carbon Management Accounting has gained prominence all around the world as major economies are taking steps to adhere to the Kyoto protocol requirements. Schaltegger & Burritt (2000) further developed an environmental accounting system based on physical and monetary environment information. [13]. They have categorized the decision making management information into short term and long term, past present and future and the nature of information being processed either regular or temporary. The framework is expected to be an aid and serve as a guide to corporate practices, accounting & carbon reporting.

Monetary Carbon Accounting

Short Term	Long Term
Carbon cost accounting, that is Ascertaining the revenue generated or cost incurred from trading of carbon Emission certificates on a periodic basis.	Accounting for carbon mitigation technologies and the adopted & capital expenditure incurred thereon.
Assessing the cost savings made on short term Carbon costing decision	Post assessment of a carbon reduction investment and How it has achieved the carbon reduction targets.
Introducing monthly carbon operating budget	Forecasting long term financial gains with permanent Reduction in carbon footprint.
Impact on revenue due to carbon costing year on year.	Investment appraisal of carbon project, benefits of the project to the Organization.

Physical Carbon Accounting

Short Term	Long Term
Daily carbon process flow accounting	Carbon capital impact accounting & calculation of Carbon footprint reduction.
Assessment of short term carbon impacts	Assessment of physical carbon investment project appraisal.
Physical carbon budgeting and green techniques introduced	Research & Development initiatives and Long term Physical carbon planning
Carbon impact budgeting in the next few accounting periods	Physical environmental investment appraisal.

The Carbon Accounting Framework Encompasses the Below Points

1. CERs at the initial stages should be treated as a contingent asset until approval is received from the UNFCCC and has to be approved by the Board and senior leadership.
2. The CDM projects expenditure should not be charged to revenue but treated as an Intangible asset.
3. United Nations Framework Convention on Climatic Change (UNFCCC) has to approve and certify the CERs and post that the CERs can be traded in the open market and treated as an inventory. CERs cannot be recognized stage wise in projects.
4. Trading of CERs will be accounted for as either profit or loss from a business. Revenues earned from the sale of CERs will be considered under Income from other sources. Organizations should provide justification for treatment as of either profit or gains or as income from other sources.
5. CERs sold to foreign companies will be accounted for on the basis of the prevailing rate of foreign exchange applicable on the period of the contract. Fluctuations in the exchange rate may be accounted as either as gain or a loss
6. The cost price of the CER should be arrived at after capitalizing all the expenditure incurred in setting up the CDM project, operating expenses related to the project. In other words, the cost of CER/CDM should be treated as a capital asset as it leads to future economic benefits in the form of cash and cash equivalents.
7. The research and development cost of CER should not be included in the cost price of the CER. It should be separately accounted as per the Indian Accounting Standard on Research & Development
8. The stock position of the CER at the end of the financial year should be disclosed and the methods used to assess the value of CER also should be disclosed. CER should be measured at the cost price or market price whichever is less. The number of CERs which have been submitted for certification should also be disclosed.
9. CERs treated as an inventory should be measured at the cost or net realizable value whichever is less. Cost of CER is the equivalent of the cost of purchase, cost of conversion and expenses incurred to bring the inventory to its present state and form. Depreciation should also be provided for the assets which are involved in the project for the reduction of CERs.
10. Materials used, work in progress, and finished goods with respect to CDM/CER project should be categorically disclosed in the Balance sheet.

Carbon Accounting Issues

Some of the accounting issues that arise are the treatment of expenditure on CDM projects, revenue recognition in the books of accounts and the value of CERs that has to be derived. The treatment of sale consideration in the books of accounts and relevant notes on it. There is no clarity with regards to the treatment of the CDM project as whether the same to be a cost center or a profit center. In the case of foreign corporations with a significant presence in India, whether the CDM project should be identified with the parent or treated separately as an independent project in India. There are two schools of thought regarding the taxability of carbon credits in India. One view considers the CERs as the incidental business income as it is generated and income earned from business processes associated with a venture or project. Accordingly, it should be taxed as Profits and gains from business or profession or Income from other sources. The other view is the consideration from the sale of CERs as a transfer of capital assets as it is a commercially acquired right granted under the Kyoto protocol. Treatment of CERs as capital assets also leads to issues in ascertaining the cost of acquisition, the date from which the holdings of CERs should be

recognized that is at the time of certification of CERs or at the time of sale of CERs. The guidance notes on Accounting for Self-Generated Certified Emission Reductions (CERs) issued in 2012[2] recommends that CERs should be treated as an asset when the communication of credit of CER is received by the generating entity. This is because at this stage the CER is a resource controlled by the generating entity and the entity will derive economic benefits from the sale. There are divergent opinions as some experts feel that the future economic benefits are not assured. Therefore, the probability of expected future benefits should be considered in Financial Statements. The CERs also do not fall under the class or the definition of 'Intangible assets' as per Accounting Standards (AS) 26 because they are not held for the production or supply of goods and services, or for renting to others and on the contrary, they are held for sale. It may be mentioned that the issue of CERs has to undergo a verification process at UNFCCC. The generating entity may have started to reduce emissions but the same is pending approval from the UNFCCC. In such scenario, the CERs should be treated as a contingent asset as per guidelines of accounting standards (AS) 29, Provisions, contingent assets, and contingent liabilities. CERs once certified should be accounted for and valued as per AS2 at cost or net realizable value. Since CERs are recognized as inventories, the entity should apply AS 9 to recognize revenue in respect of the sale of CERs. Further, if an Organization uses any tangible assets along with CERs, it should be accounted as per provisions of Accounting Standard (AS) 10, Tangible fixed assets. Also in case an asset related to CER is retired or scrapped, it may be reviewed in accordance with the guidelines on Impairment of assets (AS) 28. The CERs may be classified as inventory in the Balance sheet showing separately the number of CERs held as inventory, numbers under certification and the amount of depreciation, operating and maintenance costs on emission reduction equipment provided for during the year.

Carbon Tax

Several approaches have been suggested for a carbon tax. First, Social cost of carbon approach (SCC) which is the present value of future damages from one unit of additional carbon released in the atmosphere. More appropriately it can be defined as the incremental damage or cost to the society from the emission of one ton of CO₂ at a particular point of time. The social cost may be assessed as the damages the carbon emission causes to public health, natural productivity, damages to the public property, rise in heat levels or adverse environmental deterioration it causes to the ecology. This approach uses the tax rate as equivalent to the social cost of carbon or the optimal tax should equalize the marginal social cost of carbon emission. The SCC approach has a great disadvantage in terms of estimating the social cost of carbon, national and international climate policies, value to be considered for natural disasters, future damages, etc. The estimation involves uncertainty and would require advanced mathematical modeling and assumptions. The other conceptual issue is the determination or the consideration of the domestic impact or the worldwide impact as climate change and emissions equally affect all nations. The second approach is the abatement approach where the carbon tax aims to meet the specific emission reduction targets. The lower the emission the lower the tax rates, incentives, and vice versa. The third approach is identifying the proxies for carbon emissions which could be taxed effectively. For example, the carbon content of fuels is the best proxy for carbon dioxide emissions. Designing the tax rate is the most crucial element in carbon tax structure design and also its administration. The issue is the measurement and quantification of social costs. Broadening the carbon tax base would expose the corporate groups to tax liability which could have repercussions in the form of political opposition to the tax. Further, the administrative and bureaucratic hurdles associated with monitoring and assessing the emissions could be sufficiently high making the imposition of carbon tax unjustifiable. There are few obvious questions that must be answered before legislating on the carbon tax. (1) Which gases or fuels

should be targeted for tax? (2) What would be the carbon tax assessment mechanism? (3) What should be the revenue sharing agreement between the Centre and the States? (4) What exemptions, refunds or credits should be provided to offset the tax? (5) What point in the value or supply chain the tax should be levied, that is upstream at the point of fuel production or downstream at the point of fuel consumption or the hybrid approach? For example, for coal, it will be the mine, petroleum at the refinery and natural gas at the processing facilities or at the retail fuel stations or electricity grids where the ultimate consumers purchase the product. (6) How to neutralize the regressive nature of carbon tax as it involves high cost in the form of higher energy for the customers? (7) What to do with the revenues generated by a carbon tax, that is the revenue allocation decision in the form of rebates, applied toward tax cuts, promote emission mitigation projects, spending on Governmental policy goals other than environmental or the general deficit reduction? (8) What should be the initial carbon tax rate and how it should change over the period of time? (9) What should be the basis for determining the incentives for producers to shift to renewable energy and reduce the production of carbon intensive goods and services? (10) What adjustments are required in the rate of tax according to the marginal cost and benefits of carbon abatement? Does carbon tax involve externality and tradeoffs? However, it can be argued that a carbon tax is the best weapon to mitigate climatic damage, encourage innovation in low carbon technologies and improve public finances. Economists and policymakers across the globe are discussing, offering insights for an introduction and possible solutions to address the issues anticipated in the imposition of a carbon tax.

Conclusion

Carbon trading is an extremely new concept in a nascent stage and would require serious government policy initiatives and interventions. The Government intent in supporting the capping of emissions is important or else the market of carbon trading will cease to exist. There could also be problems of excess demand and supply of carbon units that are to be traded which could result in a distortion in the price of carbon credits. The emission caps will need to be highly regulated by the Government. The carbon trade accounting has become an important issue for Indian Corporate houses. The guidance notes released by The Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI) do not address the potential problems that could emerge under the other two mechanisms of Kyoto protocol that is the Joint Implementation efforts and the International Emissions Trading. Additionally, the guidance notes released only talk about self-generated CERs. The accounting principles related to recognition, measurement, and disclosures under the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) and silent on the accounting aspects of purchased CERs and the use of CERs in their own business. The accounting and principles underlying the treatment of carbon credit in all of the three mechanisms could vary significantly. Till the new guidelines are released different entities will have to apply judgments from auditors based on transactions executed in carbon credits and multiple interpretations could undermine the basic objective of uniformity of accounting principles.

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